

Feasibility of Muography applied to a catalytic hydrotreatment tower

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Abstract. In this work, the feasibility of applying Muography to a catalytic hydrotreatment tower was evaluated. Specifically, it was determined whether it is possible to detect changes in the density of the material composing the fixed bed of these towers when they become non-functional due to the accumulation of residues. For this purpose, simulations were carried out by injecting a flux of muons through the material and counting the changes this flux undergoes due to increases in density and finally a dispersion in these data was simulated to determine if it is feasible to distinguish between different densities.

1. Introduction

Primary particles of cosmic rays, such as protons and atomic nuclei, trigger various nuclear reactions when interacting with the atoms of the atmosphere. These reactions produce secondary particles in a process known as an atmospheric particle cascade. The resulting particles, such as pions, muons, electrons, and photons, travel through the atmosphere and can reach the Earth's surface [7].

The components of this cascade are primarily classified into electromagnetic and hadronic; it is in the latter where a considerable flux of muons (a fundamental particle) is produced through the decay of pions and kaons.

Figure 1. Components of Atmospheric cascades [6].

Muons, which have a mass approximately 200 times greater than that of electrons, are relatively stable with a half-life of 2.2 microseconds. Due to their high energy and penetrability, muons can travel great distances through the atmosphere and penetrate deeply into any body, reaching up to kilometers in rock. Because of these properties, muons are valuable for the detection of cosmic rays and the study of astrophysical phenomena, as well as for their application in high-energy physics [5].

I	II	III
<p>Electrón</p> <p>e^-</p> <p>Masa: 0.511 MeV/c²</p> <p>q_e : -1 s: 1/2</p>	<p>Muon</p> <p>μ^-</p> <p>Masa: 105.67 MeV/c²</p> <p>q_e : -1 s: 1/2</p>	<p>Tau</p> <p>τ^-</p> <p>Masa: 1.77 GeV/c²</p> <p>q_e : -1 s: 1/2</p>
<p>Neutrino del electrón</p> <p>ν_e</p> <p>Masa: < 2.2 eV/c²</p> <p>q_e : 0 s: 1/2</p>	<p>Neutrino del muon</p> <p>ν_μ</p> <p>Masa: < 0.17 MeV/c²</p> <p>q_e : 0 s: 1/2</p>	<p>Neutrino del tau</p> <p>ν_τ</p> <p>Masa: < 15.5 MeV/c²</p> <p>q_e : 0 s: 1/2</p>

Figure 2. Properties of the Muon [1].

1.1 Muography

One of the main applications of atmospheric muon detection is Muography. This is an imaging technique used to visualize the interior of solid structures; it is based on detecting the attenuation of the muon flux as it passes through an object, similar to how X-rays are used in radiography. The following sections will present the main concepts used in Muography:

Opacity along a path L is defined as:

$$\varrho(L) = \int_L \rho(\xi) d\xi \quad (1)$$

Thus, when muons traverse a target, only those that exceed a certain threshold energy E_{\min} for a given opacity in a specific direction will pass through. The expression for this minimum energy is calculated as follows:

$$E_{\min} + \int_0^{\varrho} \frac{dE}{d\varrho} d\varrho = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where $\frac{dE}{d\varrho}$ represents the energy loss along the optical path (which can be approximated by the Bethe-Bloch formula for preliminary calculations).

Thus, the integrated flux passing through the target is given by:

$$I(\varrho, \theta) = \int_{E_{\min}(\varrho)}^{\infty} \Phi(E, \theta) dE \quad (3)$$

Where $\Phi(E, \theta)$ represents the muon spectrum at the study location

1.1 Potential Application in the Oil Industry

At the Industrial University of Santander in Colombia, the possibility of applying muography to a catalytic hydrotreatment tower is being studied due to the impracticality of other techniques. The problem lies in the accumulation of residues produced by these towers when processing diesel, reaching a point where the tower must stop quickly. Thus, the objective of this technique would be to predict the shutdown time of these towers by monitoring changes in density, which in turn change the optical depth in a given direction.

Figure 3. Diagram of the Interior of a Fixed-Bed Hydrotreatment Tower [3].

For the detection of muon flux through this structure, a two-panel hodoscope is proposed.

Figure 4. Diagram of a Two-Panel Hodoscope for Muography [2].

The flux through the hodoscope can be calculated by summing trackings with a fixed direction r_{ij} , that is:

$$N_{ij} = \Delta t x T_{ij} x I(\varrho) \quad (4)$$

Where:

T_{ij} : Acceptance that depends on the solid angle and the area defined by r_{ij} in the hodoscope

Δt : Observation duration

Figure 5. Trackings r_{ij} in the construction of a Muography

If we define the variation in flux due to the increase in density as:

$$\Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho) = I(\rho + \delta\rho) - I(\rho) \quad (5)$$

Then, the condition according to N. Lesparre [4] for detecting such a change is:

$$\Delta t x T_{ij} x \frac{(\Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho))^2}{I(\rho)} > n^2 \quad (6)$$

Where "n" is the number of sigmas for the confidence interval.

Taking N. Lesparre's condition and rewriting it in terms of the number of expected muons in r_{ij} :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N_{ij}}{I(\rho)} x \frac{(\Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho))^2}{I(\rho)} &> n^2 \\ \rightarrow N_{ij} &> \frac{n^2}{\left(\frac{\Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho)}{I(\rho)}\right)^2} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the detectability condition is one in which, given a density difference, it is sought that in each direction N_{ij} exceeds this threshold. Thus, with a greater change in density, less observation time is required.

2. Methodology

For the potential application, this work evaluated the feasibility of muography by studying the possibility of detecting expected density changes in a typical hydrotreatment tower using a hodoscope. Next, the methodology used will be explained.

We take an ideal detector plane for a certain direction, of area A , and calculate the number of muons that enter this surface:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= I(\rho) x \delta\Omega x A x \Delta t \\ \Delta N &= \Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho) x \delta\Omega x A x \Delta t \\ \rightarrow \frac{\Delta N}{N} &= \frac{\Delta I(\rho, \delta\rho)}{I(\rho)} \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 6. Ideal plane for muon counting

Therefore, the problem of detecting density changes through flux variations is equivalent to detecting them through changes in the detected muon count ΔN . To address this, it was proposed to pass a uniform flux (sufficient for theoretical purposes) through a cylinder representing the tower under study, in order to calculate changes in the muon count passing through the tower after attenuation. Subsequently, data dispersion was simulated to assess the ability to distinguish one count from another, thereby detecting changes in density. For this purpose, four configurations were implemented representing the main directions from which muon flux can be counted.

Figure 7. Diagram of the 4 configurations implemented for the model

The first part involves calculating the maximum expected density increases considering properties of Diesel and its generated residues. The second stage is the construction of a model in the Meiga framework, which consists of simulating the passage of a muon flux through the target (the tower) to obtain an attenuation count.

2.1 Estimates of expected densities in the catalytic hydrotreatment tower

The properties of the pellets comprising the typical fixed bed are typically [8]:

Table 1. Typical properties of the pellets in the fixed bed.

	% mass	density (g/cm ³)
Al ₂ O ₃	76 %	1.5
MoO ₃	20 %	2.5
NiO	4 %	3.5
v _p	0.4 %	cm ³ /g

The real and bulk density of the pellet based on its components are calculated using the expressions:

$$\rho_{ca} = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{\%m_k}{\rho_k}}; \rho_{ca}^A = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\rho_{ca}} + v_p} \quad (9)$$

With this, we obtain $\rho_{ca} = 4.15 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $\rho_{ca}^A = 1.56 \text{ g/cm}^3$

The cylindrical pellet has pores and active elements (only on its surface) as shown in the following diagram:

Figure 8. Components present in the pellet before its use

The interior is mainly Al and O due to the alumina matrix. Once the pellet is saturated with residues, the component distribution is as shown in the following diagram:

Figure 9. Components present in the pellet after its use

It was considered that the residues occupy additional volume in the pellet. The molar percentages for the components on the surface are [3]:

Table 2. Distribution of components on the surface - final state.

	% mass
C ^(e)	52.3 %
Q ^(e)	19 %
Ca	10.4 %
Mo ^(e)	0.3 %
S	15.3 %
Al ^(e)	1.1 %
V ^(e)	0.6 %
Ni ^(e)	0.9 %
Na	0.1 %

And the mass percentages of internal residues are [3]:

Table 3. Distribution of components inside - final state.

Ni ⁽ⁱ⁾	C ⁽ⁱ⁾	V ⁽ⁱ⁾
6.33 %	7.49 %	3.63 %

Assuming a volume fraction available for Diesel of $\varepsilon^0 = 0.5$. Therefore, the mass percentages for the final state are:

Table 4. Mass percentages - final state.

	% mass
Al	14.9 %
O	20.5 %
Ni	7.7 %
Mo	5.0 %
V	4.4 %
C	23.8 %
Ca	10.8 %
S	12.7 %
Na	0.1 %

Now, to calculate the density of the pellet once it has been filled with residues, we use the expression:

$$\rho_{ca}^{A,r} = \frac{\Phi}{\eta} \rho_{ca}^A / \eta = 1 + \Phi \rho_{ca}^A \sum \frac{\%m_k^{(e)}}{\rho_k^{(e)}} \quad (10)$$

ϕ : fraction of final mass to initial mass of the pellet

η : fraction of final volume to initial volume of the pellet

And the void volume is reduced with the expression:

$$\varepsilon^r = 1 - \eta + \eta \varepsilon^0 \quad (11)$$

Finally, the equivalent density of the fixed bed was calculated using:

$$\rho_{eq}^0 = \varepsilon^0 \rho_{Diesel} + (1 - \varepsilon^0) \rho_{ca}^A \quad (12)$$

$$\rho_{eq}^r = \varepsilon^r \rho_{Diesel} + (1 - \varepsilon^r) \rho_{ca}^{A,r} \quad (13)$$

With this, the materials defined for the model are summarized in the following table based on the percentage increase in density:

Table 5. Components of the sample based on the density increase - final state.

	0%	+20%	+40%	+60%	+74%
$\rho_{eq}^r (g/cm^3)$	1.205	1.446	1.688	1.928	2.097
$\rho_{ca}^{A,r} (g/cm^3)$	1.560	1.790	1.940	2.045	2.102
Al	40.22 %	27.65 %	21.04 %	17 %	15 %
O	43.3 %	31.97 %	26.025 %	22.375 %	20.52 %
Ni	3.14 %	5.41 %	6.6 %	7.33 %	7.7 %
Mo	13.34 %	9.16 %	6.97 %	5.63 %	4.97 %
V		2.2 %	3.36 %	4.07 %	4.42 %
C		11.85 %	18.07 %	21.88 %	23.78 %
Ca		5.39 %	8.22 %	9.95 %	10.82 %
S		6.34 %	9.67 %	11.71 %	12.73 %
Na		0.03 %	0.045 %	0.055 %	0.06 %
ε_0^r	50 %	36.6 %	23.2 %	9.8 %	0.4 %
Incr% in residues	0%	26.9 %	53.9 %	80.8 %	99.6 %
% mass_residues	35.27 %	21.52 %	11.69 %	4.32 %	0.16 %

2.1 Modeling

The model was implemented using the Meiga framework, which is based on Geant4 and designed for simulating detectors in high-energy physics. The structure of Meiga is depicted in the following diagram:

Figure 10. Workflow diagram of Meiga

An important factor to consider is that Meiga simulates the interaction of muons with matter directly, using quantum field theory to solve the problem.

The hydrotreatment unit was modeled as a hollow cylinder of steel, 4m in diameter and 12m in height; the coating consisted of 24mm of steel, 100mm of insulation, and 1mm of aluminum. The interior material was modeled with the properties shown in Table 05.

Figure 11. Configurations built in the model

3. Results

The simulations were conducted with an injection of 100,000 muons, which took approximately one hour of processing time per case. Muons that passed through the tower were counted.

Below are the results of 16 simulations performed to calculate the percentage variation in muon flux count through the tower based on the percentage change in density.

Figure 12. Variation in the muon count for Configuration C1

Figure 13. Variation in the muon count for Configuration C2

Figure 14. Variation in the muon count for Configuration C3

Figure 15. Variation in the muon count for Configuration C4

With this, it is found that the most noticeable variation is in Configuration C3, with 3.82%. Therefore, three simulations were conducted for each density change to evaluate the dispersion of the results.

Figure 16. Muon count with repeated simulations - Configuration C3

Figure 17. Percentage variation in the number of muons - Configuration C3 - average 3.86%

From this, it can be observed that for the considered percentage increases and the number of simulations conducted, density variations starting from 20% are distinguishable. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that the configurations with maximum attenuation (C1 and C2) did not significantly increase the percentage variation as expected.

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